

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF AMNESTY PROGRAMMES ON THE WELL-BEING OF EX-MILITANT IN NIGER DELTA REGION, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of amnesty programmes on the well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study is to examine effect of amnesty economic empowerment and educational programmes on the well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region. Two research questions were raised to guide the study. Cross-sectional survey research design was adopted because of the nature of the study. Questionnaire is the main instruments of data collection. Data were collected from 1,200 respondents in three states in the Niger Delta Region using stratified, simple random, and purposive sampling technique. The generated data were statistically tested using linear regression. The results obtained from the analysis of data revealed that, amnesty economic empowerment, educational programmes, significantly affects well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region, Nigeria. The study concluded that there is a significant relationship between federal government amnesty programmes and well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region, Nigeria. The study recommended that Government (federal), and the Niger Delta Development Commission, (NDDC) should strengthen the existing skill acquisition programmes, which should be accompanied with empowerment programme that would assist beneficiaries set up their own businesses. Beneficiaries of micro-credits scheme should be monitored and mentored until they acquire enough confidence to stand on their own. Artisans, such as carpenters, mechanics and bricklayers should be given opportunities to update their knowledge and sharpen their skills through hands-on-training in established workshops. This will enhance their ability to render better services and expand their businesses to employ more people. The study concludes that amnesty programmes affect the well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region, Nigeria. (Word count: 258)

Keywords: Amnesty, programmes, well-being, ex-militants, economic empowerment, educational programmes

INTRODUCTION

The declaration of Amnesty to the Niger Delta Militants by the Federal Government of Nigeria was acknowledged as the needed roadmap to the Niger Delta crisis. It was expected to draw out the militants from the creeks for skill acquisition training and rehabilitation, end

violence, and pave the way for a comprehensive development of the long-neglected Niger Delta Region (NDR). Acceptance of the amnesty was expected to herald peace that had eluded the NDR for many years. It was supposed to end hostage taking and the demand for ransoms and bring to an end pipeline vandalization, and oil bunkering. Recent development in the NDR suggests that these expectations have been realised, with significant number of the ex-militants becoming millionaires (Ikoh & Ukpong, 2013). The amnesty programme was aim at making ex-militants comply with the law and providing them with skills, instead of punishing them for their past offences. Amnesty programme according to Kuku, (2012) in the NDR was a huge success as it promotes reconciliation between ex-militants and government; it also prevents government from spending her scare resources on prosecution, especially when massive numbers of violators are involved.

The Niger Delta after over five decades of crude oil exploitation and exploration has remained undeveloped suffering both human and ecological devastation. The Niger Deltans have expressed displeasure and discontent of their conditions through several peaceful means including appeals, petitions, and litigation (Ikoh & Ukpong, 2013). Unfortunately, the Nigerian state in gross irresponsible insensitivity has not adequately shown any sympathy for this affliction. The “struggle” emanated as a result of the people’s displeasure against perceived injustices and their exploitation by oil companies in the region. These injustices included non-provision of amenities, non-provision of employment opportunities, and the refusal or delay in the payment of compensation to communities. The struggle later on expanded to include the desire for the creation of a distinct region with a political and administrative structure for the Niger Delta (Isumonah, 2003; Kuku, 2012; Ogbogbo, 2005), as well as a greater share of the federation’s revenue than was hitherto allocated to them. The struggle involved confrontation with multi-national oil companies and the federal government. Strategies adopted by the people in the course of this “struggle” included dialogue, disagreements, violence, civil unrest, militancy, insurgency, opportunistic criminality, kidnapping, speculation, and misinformation, as well as blockade of main access to site, stoppage of dredging activity, rallies, picketing of offending oil companies, obstruction of rig from entering into location site, stoppage of location presentation, obstruction of pipeline construction, and obstruction of de-oiling exercise (Kuku, 2012; Saale, 1991).

Niger Delta youths have been in the forefront of the struggle since the first revolt spearheaded by Isaac Adaka Boro and Chief Owonaro in 1966. The Isaac Adaka Boro group in 1966 attacked the facilities of Shell-British Petroleum and government, and ordered the closure of schools, customary courts, and other institutions. It also cancelled all agreements relating to crude oil exploration and production in the Niger Delta (Ogbogbo, 2005). Since that first revolt, other pressure groups have sprung up. They include Movement for the Survival of the Ogoni People (MOSOP), Ijaw National Congress (INC), and Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), as well as Chikoko Movement among others (Kuku, 2012). These groups spearheaded coordinated attacks on oil installations in the Niger Delta and sabotaged the activities of multi-national oil companies in the region. The Ogoni, under the aegis of the MOSOP, for instance, effectively halted the activities of oil companies in the 1980s till the grievances of the people were addressed. MOSOP was also able to mobilize communities in its fight against oil companies, and it can be said that it was responsible for engendering community activism in the struggle.

These struggles spanned over three decades and different strategies. Strategies adopted included dialogue, litigation, protest, and recourse to violence (Ogbogbo, 2005). The last two approaches were responsible for the high rate of insecurity in the region. By the time the country returned to democratic governance in 1999, youth and community restiveness in the Niger Delta had reached an all-time high. Different governments at the center made efforts aimed at combating the crisis in the Niger Delta, but these did not yield positive results. This was probably because the people of the delta did not trust government. Kuku (2012) writes, "Since independence, the people of the Niger Delta have become used to the military being deployed against them by successive military regimes." This mistrust was extended to civilian governments, especially the Obasanjo regime. His government was accused of using violence and counter violence (force and military action) to address the situation in the Niger Delta (Isumonah, 2003). In 2003, the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN), headed by President Olusegun Obasanjo, set up the Joint Task Force (JTF) in the Niger Delta, "to safeguard oil production, secure oil installations, crush community protest and deal with any activities that threaten the activities of the oil companies or personnel within the oil industry" (Kuku, 2012).

Also in 1999, President Olusegun Obasanjo ordered the leveling of Odi, a riverine community in Bayelsa state, by military personnel. It was estimated that about 2,000 people died in that military action (Human Rights Watch, 2002). Militant groups in the delta, led by Asari Dokubo of the Niger Delta Volunteer Force (NDVF) and Ateke Tom of the Niger Delta Vigilantes, retaliated with violence. In 2004, Asari Dokubo declared an all-out oil war against the Nigerian state and oil companies operating in the region; he was arrested in 2005 and charged with treason (Kuku, 2012). This was the state of things in the Niger Delta till Umar Musa Yar'Adua came into office as president in May 2007.

In an effort to bring peace and free flow of oil in the region, the federal government under the presidency of late Yar'Adua in 2008 initiated an amnesty programme for all militants in the region. The programme required militants to surrender their arms and in turn are pardoned for their activities. However, in spite of the implementation of this amnesty programme since 2008 in the region, recent reports Segun (2011) and Omon (2011) demonstrate that militancy and the attendant consequences are still experienced in the region. The amnesty components include disarmament, demobilization, and reintegration (DDR) of the ex-militants. Disarmament consists of the collection and destruction of small arms, ammunition, explosives, light and heavy weapons, while demobilization includes disarming and dismantling of militant camps. The reintegration consists of several phases: the initial camping for briefing, registration, and payment of monetary assistance to assist the ex-militants' reinsertion into the society, selection for different aspect of skill acquisition training within and outside the country, and rehabilitation that will include job placement, credit scheme, and scholarships.

The DDR component of the amnesty program is an integral part of the intervention. The amnesty program was designed and established to tackle the problem of insecurity and youth restiveness in the Niger Delta, and by implication, to restore peace and stability to the region. The disarmament, demobilisation and reintegration process was followed by a monthly stipend for the ex-militants. An initial component of the programme was the payment by government of millions of dollars to the militant leaders for handing in their weapons at the outset. All these programmes put together has gone a long way in enhancing the well-being of ex-militant in the Niger Delta region. With the introduction and implementation of the Presidential Amnesty

Programme (PAP) by the Nigerian government in 2009, which has become the euphemism for the government's Disarmament, Demobilisation, and Reintegration (DDR) policy on the Niger Delta – the direction of research naturally changed, and attention has increasingly shifted to the post-amnesty era of the Niger Delta. As such, there has been an appreciable development of literature on the topic of amnesty in the Niger Delta (Aghedo, 2013; Ushie, 2013; Eke, 2014; Obi, 2014; Agbiboa, 2014; Oluwaniyi, 2011a; Davidheiser & Kiale, 2011). Amnesty programmes enhance the well-being of ex-militants by providing disarmament, rehabilitation, and socio-economic reintegration opportunities that reduce insecurity and foster a sense of stability, dignity, and livelihood.

According to the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2008) Niger Delta is a region suffering from administrative neglect, crumbling social infrastructure and services, high unemployment, social deprivation, abject poverty, filth and squalor and economic conflict. It is against this background that various leaders of the region have been calling for a redress of this socioeconomic situation of the region in various fora. These include Ogoni Bill of Rights (1990), the Kaiama Declaration (1998), among others. Oluduro and Oluduro (2012) reported that seventy percent of the inhabitants still live in rural subsistent existence characterized by a total absence of such basic facilities as electricity, pipe-borne water, hospitals, proper housing, and motorable roads. Whereas there is hardly electricity supply in many riverine areas, telecommunication facilities are in acute short supply. Healthcare is less than desirable while the schools are ill-equipped hence they serve more as youth restive factories than institutions of learning. Waste management culture is poor and this is exacerbated by the activities of oil companies. The harsh conditions of living were part of what provoked the ex-militants to engage in proscribed activities to attract government attention. While a handful of work on the topic has indeed been useful to understanding the background, challenges, and sustainability of the amnesty policy as a peace strategy in the Niger Delta, the main thrust of this study is to examine the various amnesty programmes and how it has improved the well-being of ex-militants in Niger Delta Region. The following research questions were advanced to guide this study

To what extent has the amnesty economic empowerment programmes improve the well-being in terms of income level of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region?

How does amnesty educational programmes affect the well-being in terms of literacy level of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region?

Objectives of study

The general objective of this study is to examine the effect of amnesty programmes on the well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region, Nigeria. Specifically, the study is designed to determine:

The effect of amnesty economic empowerment programmes on the well-being in terms of income level of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region

The effect of amnesty educational programmes on the well-being of literacy level ex-militant in Niger Delta Region

Hypotheses of study

Amnesty economic empowerment programmes has not significantly improve the well-being in terms of income level of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region

Amnesty educational programmes has not significantly affect the well-being in terms of literacy level of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region

Methods

The study adopted cross sectional survey design. This design is considered appropriate for this study because it has the capacity to adequately and accurately gather necessary information within a given timeframe. Furthermore, the design is economical and focuses on studying large and small populations with emphasis on relative incidence, distribution and interrelations of sociological and psychological variables. Niger Delta is a region that spreads out to cover the South-eastern part of Nigeria in West Africa. It is also referred to as the South-South geopolitical zone in the current six geo-political structure of the country. Niger Delta is an area of dense mangrove rainforest in the southern tip of Nigeria comprising nine states out of the thirty six, including the FCT that make up the entity called Nigeria. The region alone takes 25% of the total number of the states in Nigeria. It is the nucleus of Nigeria's wealth and one of the world's energy sources because it is rich in oil and gas resources, which directly supports the country's economy. The Delta of the Niger River in Nigeria is a densely populated region, sometimes called the Oil Rivers, because it was once a major producer of palm oil. The area was the British Oil River Protectorate from 1885 until 1893 when it was expanded and became the Niger Coast Protectorate.

The population of the study comprised respondents residing in the Niger Delta Region, Nigeria. The study population consist respondents aged 18 years and above. The study adopted stratified sampling technique, simple random, and purposive sampling technique. The study adopted stratified sampling technique because it reduces sampling error as it enabled the researcher to identify and consider the heterogeneous characteristics of the population while drawing the sample. The stratified sampling technique was used in the stratification of the Niger Delta Region into nine different strata. From the nine (9) strata, the balloting method of the simple random sampling technique was used in selecting three states from nine existing states that make up the Niger Delta Region. For the purpose of this study Rivers, Delta, and Bayelsa was selected. The three states were selected based on their relevance in the Niger Delta area and the fact that youth restive and militancy featured predominately in these three states. From the three selected states two local government areas were selected through the balloting method of the simple random sampling technique. A total of six (6) local government areas were selected. From the six (6) local government area, two communities were selected from each of the local government area. This brings the total number of communities to twelve (12) communities. Simple random technique is adopted because it gives all the elements equal opportunity of being sampled for the study without any bias.

In addition, the purposive sampling technique was used in the selection of respondents. The purposive sampling technique was adopted because it prevents unnecessary and irrelevant items entering into the sample per chance. From each of the selected communities thirty two (32) respondents were selected. This brings the total number of respondents selected for this

study to one thousand two hundred (1200) respondents. The Taro Yamane sample determinant was used in this study.

The sample size for this study consists one thousand two hundred (1200) respondents purposively drawn from three (3) states in the Niger Delta Region, Nigeria. Thirty two (32) respondents were selected from each of the twelve (12) communities to make up the sample size of 1200 respondents. The sample comprises of civil servants, farmers, fisher men, traders and artisans who are living in the study area. The questionnaire was adopted as main instrument for data collection. The questionnaire consists of 21 items, and it entitled “Questionnaire on Amnesty programme and well-being of ex-militants (QAPWE)”. The questionnaire was divided into three main units. Section A, elicited information on the respondents personal demography such as sex, age, marital status, educational level, level of experience, and place of residence. Section B, consists of 10 items designed to measure the various programmes under Amnesty programme; each require the respondent to indicate the frequency of their responses on a four point Likert-scale – Strongly Agree[SA], Agree [A], Disagree [D], Strongly Disagree [SD] scale. Well-being was measured in terms of income level and literacy level. Data collected were edited, coded, and analysed using appropriate statistical methods. Frequency distribution, simple percentages and Linear Regression analysis procedure was applied in analysing the generated data.

Results

Research question one

To what extent has the amnesty economic empowerment programmes improve the well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region? Descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) was used to answer the research question. Participants’ responses are presented in table 1

Table 1

Response on amnesty empowerment programmes and the well-being of ex-militant

S/N	AMNESTY EMPOWERMENT PROGRAMME AND WELL-BEING OF EX-MILITANTS	SA	A	D	SD
1	Ex-militant had access to grants made available by amnesty programme	492 (43.00)	549 (47.38)	66 (5.72)	45 (3.90)
2	Ex-militants were given sewing machines after their rehabilitation programme	402 (34.89)	486 (42.18)	156 (13.54)	168 (9.37)
3	Catering equipment were made available to ex-militant after their rehabilitation programme	432 (37.5)	495 (42.96)	129 (11.19)	66 (5.72)
4	Computer sets were distributed to ex-militants who had knowledge in computer operation	414 (35.93)	369 (32.03)	213 (18.48)	156 (13.54)
5	Ex-militants were paid monthly allowances for their upkeep	582 (50.52)	432 (37.50)	84 (7.29)	54 (4.68)

Source: Field survey, 2023

Research question two

How does amnesty educational programmes affect the well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region? Descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) was used to answer the research question. Participants' responses are presented in table 2

TABLE 2

Response on amnesty educational programmes and the well-being of ex-militant					
S/N	AMNESTY EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMME AND WELL-BEING OF EX-MILITANTS	SA	A	D	SD
6	Scholarships were given to repentant militants who indicated interest in furthering their education	522 (45.31)	555 (48.17)	30 (2.60)	45 (3.90)
7	Repentant militant were send abroad for studies in various professional programmes like engineering	492 (43.00)	549 (47.38)	57 (4.94)	54 (4.68)
8	Special attention was given to repentant militants who indicated interest in studying oil and gas	582 (50.52)	432 (37.50)	84 (7.29)	54 (4.68)
9	The amnesty educational programme is not limited to ex-militants who are interested in science disciplines alone	156 (13.54)	414 (35.93)	369 (32.03)	213 (18.48)
10	The number of ex-militants who indicated interest to go back to school was high	564 (49.00)	483 (42.00)	66 (5.72)	39 (3.38)

Source: Field survey, 2023

Test of hypotheses

Hypothesis one

Amnesty economic empowerment programmes has not significantly improve the well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region. The independent variable in this hypothesis is economic empowerment programmes, while the dependent variable is well-being of ex-militant. Simple linear regression statistics was used to test this hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance and the result is presented in table 3.

The result of analysis as presented in table 3 revealed that the R-value of 0.281a is significant at 0.05 alpha level (p-value of 0.001 is less than 0.05) hence the stated null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between amnesty economic empowerment programmes and well-being of ex-militants. Also, the R² -value of .077 implies that 77% of total variance is accounted for by the predictor variable (economic empowerment programmes). Furthermore, the regression ANOVA is significant, showing that there is a significant linear association (contribution) of the predictor variable (economic empowerment programmes) and well-being of ex-militants given by the F-ratio (1, 1150) = 19.559; $p < 0.05$. The adjusted R² (0.76) shows some shrinkage of the unadjusted value (0.77) indicating that the model could be generalized on the population. Based on the results, it was concluded that amnesty economic empowerment programmes could significantly improve well-being of ex-militants in Niger Delta Region.

TABLE 3
Summary simple linear regression analysis of contribution of economic empowerment to well-being of ex-militants

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
Economic empowerment	12.3815	4.10366
Well-being of ex-militant	24.7861	8.26809

Model	Sum of Squares	df	F	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Sig
Regression	2499.231	1	19.559	.281a	.077	.076	.000a
Residual	29084.942	1150					
Total	31584.173	1151					

Hypothesis two

Amnesty educational programmes does not significantly contribute to the well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region. The independent variable in this hypothesis is educational programmes, while the dependent variable is well-being of ex-militant. Simple linear regression statistics was used to test this hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance and the result is presented in table 4.

The result of analysis as presented in table 4, revealed that the R-value of 0. 227a is significant at 0.05 alpha level (p-value of 0.000a is less than 0.05) hence the stated null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between amnesty educational programmes and well-being of ex-militants. Also, the R² –value of .069 implies that 69% of total variance is accounted for by the predictor variable (educational programmes). Furthermore, the regression ANOVA is significant, showing that there is a significant linear association (contribution) of the predictor variable (educational programmes) and well-being of ex-militants given by the F-ratio (1, 1150) = 14.958; $p < 0.05$. The adjusted R² (0.68) shows some shrinkage of the unadjusted value (0.69) indicating that the model could be generalized on the population. Based on the results, it was concluded that amnesty educational programmes could significantly improve well-being of ex-militants in Niger Delta Region.

TABLE 4
Summary simple linear regression analysis of contribution of educational programmes to well-being of ex-militants

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation					
Educational programmes	14.3873	5.22361					
Well-being of ex-militants	24.7861	8.26809					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	F	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Sig
Regression	1231.612	1	14.958	.227a	.069	.068	.000a
Residual	30352.562	1150					
Total	31584.173	1151					

Discussion of findings

Amnesty economic empowerment programmes and well-being of ex-militant

From the result of hypothesis one, the study shows that amnesty economic empowerment programmes significantly improve the well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region, Nigeria. The study revealed that ex-militant had access to grants made available by amnesty programme. Similarly, the study revealed that ex-agitators were provided with equipment such as sewing machines, catering materials, computers among others. Girigiri (2000) reported that a significant association exists between provision of credit facilities, poverty alleviation and crime control. The provision of credit facilities helps individuals out of their economic predicaments and makes them responsible citizens. Abdulahi (2012) noted that provision of credit facilities to youths who possess skill have tremendously reduced poverty and crime, as well as improve their living standard. Access to credit facilities in recent times have become one of the most efficient vehicles for the effective mobilization of young entrepreneur and discouraging youth involvement in crime (Girigiri, 2000).

Educational programme and well-being of ex-militant

Findings of this study indicate that amnesty educational programmes significantly affect the well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region. Obasi (1998) asserts that education is an indispensable tool for the improvement of life and well-being of individuals. It helps in the improvement of life of an individual as well as that of the community and the society at large. When education is inculcated into the community. Its aim is always to produce people who can choose for themselves the kind of development and self-actualization they want to undertake. Eheazu (1998) noted that adult education introduced by Amnesty programme is an alternative and/or intervention education designed to take care of illiterate non-beneficiaries and dropouts of formal education who would be susceptible to any kind of lure into any of the militant groups.

It could be understood that the former militants were lured into the militant activities because of most of them are illiterate, semi-literate, unemployment, unskilled, semi-skilled and have their minds not positively developed and inclined towards national development. They found themselves idle and therefore useful to all kinds of the unlawful activities to which they are exposed.

Conclusion

This survey examined the effect of amnesty programmes on the well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region, Nigeria. Emphasis was on the relationship between amnesty skills acquisition programmes, amnesty economic empowerment programmes, amnesty educational programmes, amnesty job placement and well-being of ex-militants. After extensive statistical analysis of each of the formulated hypotheses, which guided the study, the following conclusions were arrived at:

Amnesty economic empowerment programmes significantly affects the well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region

Amnesty educational programmes significantly affect the well-being of ex-militant in Niger Delta Region

Recommendations

The Government and NDDC should develop skill acquisition programmes that should be accompanied with empowerment programmes that would assist beneficiaries set up their own businesses. Beneficiaries of micro-credits scheme should be monitored and given continuous advice until they must have developed enough confidence to run their business on their own. Opportunities should be created where artisans such as mechanics, welders, bricklayers etc., are given opportunity to update and sharpen their skills and knowledge through on hands training in training workshops. This will boost their capability to render better and improved services to customers and expand their business and enable them employ people to work for them.

The delivery of basic infrastructure in the Niger Delta region is a indispensable element for the reduction of poverty and sustainable development in the region. Therefore, government and other stakeholders should improve on road repairs and construction to enable more connectivity between rural and urban dwellers.

Government agencies in charge of this projects and NDDC management should make sure that these projects must be completed as they will positively affect the lives of the people. Also, contractors who have left their projects uncompleted must be forced and given ultimatum to complete the project or face the law. The Also, government and the NDDC commission should revise the fund allocated to the commission and also fortify its accountability procedures and ensure that contractors are paid on time, as well as check the mismanagement and misappropriation of resources.

REFERENCES

- Agbiboa, D. (2014). Transformational strategy or gilded pacification? Four years on: The Niger Delta armed conflict and the DDR process of the Nigerian Amnesty Programme. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*, 2014, pp. 1–25.
- Aghedo, I. (2013). Winning the war, losing the peace: Amnesty and the challenges of postconflict peace-building in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*, 48 (3), pp. 267–280.
- Davidheiser, M. & Kiale N. (2011). Demobilization or remobilization? The amnesty program and the search for peace in the Niger Delta. *African Security*, 4, pp. 44–64
- Eke, S. (2014). ‘No pay, no peace’: Political settlement and post-amnesty violence in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*, 10 (1177), pp. 1–15.
- Ikoh, M. U. & Ukpog, E. A. (2013). The Niger Delta crisis: Taming violence beyond the amnesty. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3 (17), 146-159
- Isumonah, V. (2003). The Obasanjo administration and the management of Niger Delta conflicts in Nigeria. *African Journal of Peace and Conflict Studies*, 1, 210-225.
- Kuku, K. (2012). *Remaking the Niger Delta: Challenges and opportunities*. Surrey, UK: Mandingo Publishing.
- Obi, C. (2014). Oil and the post-amnesty programme (PAP): What prospects for sustainable development and peace in the Niger Delta? *Review of African Political Economy*, 41 (140), 249–263.
- Ogbogbo, C. (2005). The Niger Delta peoples and the resource control conflict, 1960-1995: An assessment of conflict handling styles. *Perspectives on Peace and Conflict in Africa: Essays in Honor of General (Dr.) Abdulsalami A. Abubakar*, 1, 169-180
- Oluwaniyi, O. (2011a). Post-amnesty programme in the Niger Delta: Challenges and prospects. *Conflict Trends*, 4, pp. 46–54.